

ASIDE

***PROFESSIONAL USE OF INFORMATION
AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY
- BASED SOLUTIONS FOR SOCIAL
INTEGRATION***

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REPORT I

**Adult Social Inclusion in a Digital Environment
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PROFESSIONAL USE OF ICT- BASED SOLUTIONS FOR SOCIAL INTEGRATION

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Introduction

In the era of ubiquitous modern information and communication technologies (ICT), these tools and methods cannot be missing in the process of adult education. Modern adult education is moving away from teaching encyclopaedism in favour of combining traditional lecture methods with the use of Information and Communication Technology, with active group work methods, workshops, trainings and moderation methods.

Modern adult education is one in which the educator does not have the "one right" role and the only effective method of education. In return, as a trainer, facilitator or moderator, he/she uses the personal interests, experience and internal motivation of adults to learn. By creating a positive and supportive learning environment, it motivates an adult student to learn independently, inspires and strengthens learning processes. The learner, thanks to such activities of the educator, independently manages the process of learning and development, strengthens self-esteem, and therefore self-esteem¹.

Adult education in the 21st century faces many new challenges that result from the growing possibilities of using and integrating ICT in every aspect of both professional and personal life. The great potential lies in the development of ICT integration in the professional environment and the activation of professional life and adult education.

An important and key element of adult education is strengthening education to adapt it to local conditions with the possibility of global use and modelling effective practices. In the digital age, the competences of adult educators in the field of ICT enjoy great research interest because adult educators play a key role in promoting the use of ICT by adults in a variety of situations.

The aim of the study is to consider, based on literature and four case studies, the use and assessment of practices using ICT in Poland as a lever for educational change and innovation. With each case study, we include suggestions for more effective linking research and practice based on international analyses carried out covering the following countries: Poland, Spain, The Czech Republic and Turkey.

Luis Ochoa Siguencia

¹ Mikołajczyk Katarzyna, „Nowe trendy w kształceniu dorosłych”, Ośrodek Rozwoju Edukacji maj 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333339666_Katarzyna_Mikolajczyk_Nowe_trendy_w_ksztalceniu_doroslych Accessed 13.01.2020

1. Professional use of ICT- based solutions for social integration: The Polish case [Responsible: Renata Ochoa-Daderska, Agnieszka Chęcińska-Kopiec, Luis Ochoa Siguencia, INBIE]

Adult education in the area of ICT and new technologies brings several challenges, especially relevant to seniors. For the broader context of the selection of the age group of seniors, it is worth considering, in addition to age, additional social and economic elements, such as place of residence, education or purchasing power, which may affect the real needs of this group; it is worth, if possible, reaching for e.g. psychographic aspects to build a more complete picture of the senior based on the way of spending free time, interests, personality type or even more detailed aspects such as attitude to technical innovations.

Thanks to these elements, it is possible to more accurately distinguish subgroups and better identify the needs of seniors in order to more accurately adjust both the educational offer and the strategy of using the opportunities that the contemporary market of digital products and services brings (both 60-year-olds and people in their nineties participated in the activities).

Efficiency in searching for effective solutions increases thanks to participatory design (co-design). It is particularly important when designing services and products based on new technologies, addressed to seniors. The second important issue is the intergenerational aspect and the related breaking of intergroup and generational stereotypes. In this context, one should also remember about the other side of interaction, i.e. young people.

These include a variety of people from volunteers skilled in ICT to entrepreneurs, programmers and designers creating digital solutions. They often see the potential inherent in the silver economy, but equally often they are victims of stereotypical thinking about seniors by offering them services that they believe are needed by seniors.

For example, in one of the research activities a group of young programmers and designers emerged who had difficulty seeing more than just the end customer in the senior group; these teams have prepared cliché solutions based on stereotypical thinking about seniors and their needs. On the other hand, some young teams were able to break through and apply an open enough approach to see the elderly as a potential partner that allows them to better penetrate into the essence of real problems that the target group is facing.

Thanks to joint action not only the inter-group stereotypes were broken, but real needs were discovered and better solutions were proposed. The intergenerational participatory approach enables direct interaction between solution developers and potential recipients, providing benefits to both parties.

Thanks to the unconventional approach, seniors have completely new possibilities of contact with the latest technologies, which go far beyond standard forms of adult education dominating in relation to seniors. For example, seniors have repeatedly participated in tasks

related to the co-creation of new ICT solutions, from developing the content of courses, through co-creating mobile applications with young programmers to applying the latest trends such as virtual and augmented reality (VR, AR) and voice assistants (VA).

In conclusion, Living Lab's activity is an example of unconventional educational activities for seniors, based on an active participatory approach to new technologies and the silver economy. Remember to consider seniors not only as recipients, but also as potential partners who can contribute to the solution.

On the other hand, this approach requires the inclusion of young /adult entrepreneurs, designers and programmers, or even volunteers as young enthusiasts of new technologies, who also need support to more widely use the potential of seniors. Such a comprehensive approach can effectively overcome inter-group stereotypes by referring to specific desires, needs and aspirations that this target group has, just like other age groups².

Picture 1: EPALE, Adult learning EU, Jul 20, 2015
 [https://twitter.com/epale_eu/status/623151647984893952]

² Kopeć Wiesław, NOWE FORMY WSPARCIA I EDUKACJI ICT SENIORÓW. 01.07.2019, <https://kometa.edu.pl/artykuly/228,nowe-formy-wsparcia-i-edukacji-ict-seniorow> Accessed 13.01.2020

2. Professional use of ICT- based solutions for social integration: The Czech Republic case [Responsible: Emil VELINOV - ITC International]

The Ministry of Education in the Czech Republic did not set and standardize the key skills of pupils in the field of information and communication technologies (ICT) even after five years from the approval of the digital education strategy. This follows from a review of the Supreme Audit Office (SAO), which examined measures and projects that were to support the development of digitalization of education at primary and secondary schools in 2011–2018.

The Ministry has made number of steps have been taken in the area of the Digital Education Strategy up to 2019. For example, Ministry of Education of the Czech Republic created a framework of digital competences of teachers, where it plans to intensively support teacher education in the area of digital technologies. A number of tutorials and workshops have been created for school ICT coordinators and the modernization of the ICT education area for the period 2015-2019. Accordingly, International Training Centre (ITC)-Prague has put lots of efforts to develop ICT courses in its portfolio for the last 4-5 years. ITC is adult education institution for in-service teacher training, established by the Czech Ministry of Education and listed in the school registry.

ITC is active on the adult education market from 1996 and has a seventeen years long experience in the education field with specialization on the innovative teaching methods for teachers and education specialist from whole EU.

ITC is a modern and dynamic company with a long tradition and professional organizational background. The mission of ITC is to provide good quality language education together with other courses in various fields. Our main goal is to provide complex services on a professional level ensuring our clients' satisfaction.

At the moment the training centre provides the following trainings to teachers, students, seniors and minority groups as follows: Going Digital, Using Tablets in the Class, ICT for Education, Social Media and Entrepreneurship, Agile Project Management, STEM, Virtual Reality and Human Resource Management and Digitalization. ICT aims at the following milestones:

- define a basic competences portfolio specifically targeted for social inclusion
- create comprehensive list of topics and practices essential for digital social inclusion initiatives/activities
- to create a network active in digital social inclusion
- improve competencies in digital social inclusion of social educators and volunteers
- improve social inclusions through digital innovation practices, innovative ICT based methods and pedagogies, online participatory models

ITC sheds a light on developing digital skills and competencies among teachers, principals and educators, who are possessing different professional background and their ages differ quite a lot. There is certain percentage of third age people, who attend ITC trainings and courses in order to keep intact with the current ICT development and in order to stay in the professional circle of educators, who are fully aware of basic ICT enhancement on the job.

3. Professional use of ICT- based solutions for social integration: The Spanish case [Responsible: Javier SANCHEZ GARCIA - EuroFUE- UJI]

Digital Agenda for Spain

On February 15, 2013, the Council of Ministers approved the Digital Agenda for Spain as the Government's strategy to develop the digital economy and society. This strategy was configured as the umbrella for all the Government's actions in the area of Telecommunications and the Information Society. The Agenda was jointly led by the Ministry of Energy, Tourism and the Digital Agenda and by the Ministry of Finance and Public Function.

The Agenda set out the roadmap for Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) and e-Government to meet the objectives of the Digital Agenda for Europe in 2015 and 2020, and incorporated specific objectives for the development of the digital economy and society in Spain.

To this end, the Digital Agenda for Spain was designed as an agile instrument that, in addition to addressing these objectives, could be adapted to the rapid technological development that characterises the ICT sector.

Objectives

Initially the Digital Agenda for Spain contained 106 lines of action structured around six major objectives:

1. To promote the deployment of networks and services to guarantee digital connectivity.
2. Develop the digital economy for the growth, competitiveness and internationalisation of Spanish companies.
3. Improve e-government and digital public services.
4. Strengthen confidence in the digital environment.
5. Promote R&D&I in the industries of the future.
6. **Promote inclusion and digital literacy and the training of new ICT professionals.**

This sixth objective try to achieve an inclusive Information Society in which citizens and professionals are well prepared to reap the benefits of intensive use of ICTs. To this end, the Agenda proposes two fundamental areas of work: promoting inclusion and digital literacy and adapting training systems for digital training and the training of new ICT professionals.

An advanced digital society requires that many of its citizens have regular access to the Internet and benefit from the opportunities it provides. To this end, the Digital Agenda for

Spain establishes the development of a Digital Inclusion and Employability Plan through public-private collaboration and with the participation of civil society.

Spanish plans made in ICT and Information Society

Overview of digital inclusion and employability plans in Spain

The Digital Agenda for Spain establishes the elaboration of Digital Inclusion and Employability Plans that integrate the largest possible number of agents, serve as an umbrella for their initiatives, join forces and multiply the effect of the measures adopted. These Plans are the result of the contributions of multiple actors, public and private, who have joined forces in the common objective of improving the quality of life of citizens and improving the competitiveness and positioning of SMEs using ICTs.

Structure of the plans

Axis I: Accessibility

The first axis of the Plans focuses on providing the population in general and certain disadvantaged groups with access to the use of the Internet and ICT tools to reduce the risk of digital exclusion.

Axis II: Literacy

The second axis works on the objective of equipping the population with basic digital skills to offer them a better quality of life, especially for older, less qualified people and those other social groups that are reluctant to use ICT.

Axis III: Equality

The third axis focuses on reducing the gender gap in the use of and access to new information technologies. The measures included are directly related to the Actions to promote the Equality of Women and Men in the Information Society.

Axis IV: Employability

The fourth axis is aimed at improving on-the-job training for new ICT professionals and professionals from other sectors. It also articulates measures to encourage entrepreneurs, SMEs and self-employed for the development of new businesses in priority ICT lines and training in skills for entrepreneurship.

The implementation of the Digital Agenda for Spain has been articulated through the following specific plans that developed the six objectives of the Digital Agenda for Spain:

1. Plan for telecommunications and ultra-fast networks to promote efficient investment in ultra-fast networks and establish the bases for achieving the European broadband objectives for 2020.
2. ICT plan in SMEs and e-business to use ICTs to improve SMEs' productivity and competitiveness and to achieve European e-business targets.
3. Plan to boost the digital economy and digital content to realise the growth potential of the digital content industry for the digital economy.
4. Plan for the internationalisation of technology companies to increase the visibility and international presence of Spanish technology-based companies.
5. Plan for confidence in the digital environment to establish a climate of confidence in the digital environment so that ICTs contribute to the economic and social development of the country.
6. Plan for development and innovation in the ICT sector to take advantage of the potential for growth and employment generation in industries of the future.
7. Plan for digital inclusion and employability to ensure that the majority of the population uses the Internet and to achieve the European objectives of digital inclusion in order to minimise the digital divide.
8. Digital public services plan to continue promoting the digitalisation of public services to achieve greater efficiency and structure.
9. National Smart Cities Plan to promote the Smart Cities technology industry in Spain and to help local entities in the transformation processes towards Smart Cities and Smart Destinations.
10. Plan to promote Language Technologies to foster the development of natural language processing and automatic translation in Spanish and co-official languages.
11. National Plan for intelligent territories that is developed based on the experiences and results derived from the implementation of the National Plan for Intelligent Cities and the consultation carried out with the different agents in the sector.

To analyse the results of these plans, the Ministry of Economic Affairs and Digital Transformation of Spain has prepared a report of Outstanding Indicators of the Digital Economy and Society, with the latest data available (2019), which shows the evolution of the main indicators on ICT use in Households and Companies in Spain (digital inclusion in Spain).

The report focuses on two topics: the equipment and use of ICT in households and the use of ICT and e-commerce in companies, both published by the National Institute of Statistics (INE). As the results are of great interest both topics are shown.

Firstly, it analyses the indicators related to households.

In 2019, household access to a broadband connection exceeded 90%, 5.1 percentage points higher than in 2018. On the opposite side, households without an Internet connection cited lack of need and low awareness as the main reasons (75.5 and 51.3 per cent respectively). The

growth in the percentage of households using mobile telephony continues in 2019 with 98.5 %.

In terms of Internet use, the percentage of users who regularly use the Internet continues to rise with 87.7%, increasing by 5 percentage points compared to 2018. Regarding the devices used to connect to the Internet, it observes that women make greater use of mobile devices than men, while men use laptops, tablets and consoles to a greater extent than women. The specific purposes for which the Internet is used include: sending and receiving e-mail (72.2%); reading or downloading newspapers (71.1%); listening to music (62.5%); making video calls (55.1%) and Internet banking (54.9%).

About software skills, there is an increase with respect to 2017 in the percentage of individuals who have basic or above basic software skills, both in women and men, reaching 57.9 % in women and 60.7 % in men.

Looking at e-commerce, the percentage of people who have bought over the Internet in the last month was 33.2%. Most individuals spent their purchases on holiday accommodation (56.1%), sports equipment (55.7%) and tickets for shows (49.2%).

With all this, the degree of confidence in the Internet for this year is considerably higher than in 2018, with 67.6% of individuals stating that they have a lot or a fair amount of confidence in the Internet, increasing by almost 9 percentage points compared to the previous year.

Finally, it should be noted that among children aged 10-15, the use of both the computer and the Internet is very high, with 89.7% and 92.9% of children using the computer and the Internet respectively. By sex, we observe that girls use new technologies to a greater extent. For this year, the percentage of girls who have a mobile phone is 67.1 % compared to 65 % of boys.

Secondly, indicators related to ICT use and e-commerce in enterprises are analysed.

The main form of business Internet access is broadband (fixed or mobile). Most businesses (43.1%) access with speeds equal to or greater than 100 Mbps.

Half of the enterprises use social media. Of these, 95% use social networks (Facebook, LinkedIn, Google+, etc) in 95% of cases, half (47%) use websites that share multimedia content (Youtube, Flickr, etc), and 38% use company blogs or microblogs.

Regarding security, the growing trend in the use of internal security systems continues, with 92.8% of companies having some kind of security system. The main types of internal security used are: up-to-date software (87.4%); data backup in a separate location (83.6%) and strong password authentication (70.6%).

Regarding electronic signatures, 80.6% of enterprises with Internet access use digital signatures, almost 4 percentage points more than in the previous year. The main reason for the use of signatures is to interact with the public administration (99.3%).

In relation to e-commerce, the percentage of businesses selling over the Internet continues to grow, reaching 33.9%, compared to 32% in 2018.

Finally, with regard to the use of advanced services, 8.31% of companies declared that they had carried out big data analyses in 2019 and 28% had purchased some cloud computing service.

4. Professional use of ICT- based solutions for social integration: The Turkish case [Responsible: Yeliz NUR AKARÇAY, Saricam Halk Egitimi Merkezi]

Technology literacy is the ability to use technology effectively to access, evaluate, integrate, create and communicate information to improve the learning process through problem solving and critical thinking. Technology literacy helps a person to communicate, solve problems, and develop lifelong learning skills to advance.

It can be seen that technology literacy is mainly related to the individual's technology ability and skills. Emphasis on ability and skill dimension is in line with the studies carried out by the European Union. Accordingly, technology literacy is defined by the European Union as the necessary qualifications to achieve digital competence and to use information and communication technologies safely and critically in business, daily life, learning and communication with individuals. This 'digital competence' is one of the eight key qualifications defined in the European Parliament and the European Union Council's Basic Competences for Lifelong Learning advice, which European citizens must develop in a community structure surrounded by information and communication technologies. It is stated these qualifications including digital competence are necessary for the individuals to realize and develop themselves, to participate in society as an active citizen and to provide employment. On the other hand, it is widely accepted by the United Nations that technology-related digital skills can help improve social inclusion, similar to the European Union's emphasis on participation in life.

While social, cultural, economic and political developments cause individuals and social needs to change constantly, the content of the literacy phenomenon created socially in the context of cultural practices also changes in the context of different needs. Literacy appears to be related to the concept of technology, especially after the latest developments in the field of information and communication technologies. Technology in every area of daily life greatly affects the way individuals live and work. In the new order, where information and communication technologies are decisive, it is important for individuals with different social, cultural or economic backgrounds to adapt to their new life and environment surrounded by technology. In order for them to exist as individuals in the society and take advantage of the opportunities provided by technology, it is inevitable for them to develop their competences in technology and to become technology literate.

This research aims to find the basic level of technology literacy and technology use case in Turkey. For this purpose, answers were sought to the question of the acquisition and use of computer and internet technology which can be seen as the basis of information and communication technologies among individuals in our country.

According to the results of the research, although there are high usage rates in some evaluation parameters, computer and internet usage rate among individuals are not sufficient yet. Compared to other segments of the society, it is observed that individuals who are already socially, culturally and economically disadvantaged, such as women, elderly, people with low education level or who are not in the labour force, still use computer and internet technologies to a limited extent. Therefore, due to the insufficient use of technology, the sector in question cannot take advantage of the possibilities available in a wide area where technology is used today. However, the social, cultural and economic development of individuals is taking place in a technology-related manner and it is accepted as a prerequisite that technology can be used in many areas. Therefore, not only the technology dimension, but the differentiation in all areas of life is growing, which creates a deeper gap among individuals every day.

On the other hand, a more hopeless finding is encountered when the results of the research are evaluated in terms of problem-solving skills in technology intensive environments. According to the results, individuals between the ages of 16 and 65 appear to have the lowest level of competences in terms of problem-solving skills in technology-intensive environments (only 0.9% of individuals are included in the upper-level skill class). Turkey received far behind the OECD average scores in each rating level. Accordingly, it is not possible to talk about a technology literacy, which is commonly defined in the literature, as an individual who is aware of the technology, acquires the ability to use technology and develops critical thinking.

The factors affecting digital competence performance of adult people in Turkey:

Formal education background of adult people: Information Technologies and Software Courses were removed from the list of elective courses and included among compulsory courses in 2012. When the adult people are evaluated in terms of age, it is possible to say that most of them did not receive any training on computer skills in formal education since there was no information and communication technologies course among compulsory courses. Not having basic computer skills in formal education affects the use of technology negatively. However, some of the adult people use information technologies in their daily and work lives with mobile or computer-based tools. However, they may not have received any training for this use. So, it is possible to say that the use of technology is learned by trying especially in business life.

Social Prejudices: There are some social barriers like prejudices or dogmas preventing people from connecting to the internet in terms of digital competences. The wrong belief that the Internet will teach some wrong behaviours, even if the internet was not used in the formal education period, not using it afterwards can negatively affect the acquisition and updating of skills.

Bias against using technological tools: Especially senior adults may be hesitant about using technological devices. Today, the internet is seen as the shortest way to access information. However, the limited use of information and communication technologies by adults can lead to the lack of access to up-to-date information and this situation can affect the ability to use

technological tools which is seen as the fastest way to access information. In addition, online fraud situations cause adults to be cautious about performing certain transactions with technological tools.

In our country, it is seen that people's perception of old age is earlier than Europe. In countries like Germany, while people in their fifties are trying to find a second or third job to stay in the labour force or to be active, the fact that people of the same age group in our country identify themselves as elderly also affects learning. Studies in the literature have proved that today's adults who have not been exposed to information technologies since the day they were born experience difficulties in adapting to this new world from time to time, but this adaptation was easy for the generation Y who was born between 1980-2000 and has witnessed the development of technology since childhood.

Psychological barriers:

The belief that learning will slow down as you get older or that it will not be learned after a while and lack of motivation and self-confidence preventing acquiring new skills are serious psychological barriers in the use and learning of digital skills.

In addition to the external factors affecting the educational environment, people's hesitant approach towards the use of technology due to their own habits, lack of self-confidence, fears, and the fact that lifelong learning could not be internalized emerged as another dimension of the table. Not having basic skills cause some problems such as not being able to make certain inferences, not establishing a relationship between events, and not being able to access information in a world where the information required by daily life is rapidly transferred to the digital environment.

In addition to the traditional definition and meaning of literacy, technology literacy can be seen as a tool for inclusion in society, taking into account the emphasis made by international institutions and organizations such as the European Union or the United Nations. In addition to the inclusion of technology related to this phenomenon and the expansion of the concept content, the natural consequence of the individual's self-actualization will depend on her/his ability to use technology today. For this reason, reaching information and communication technologies in our country, obtaining these technologies, integrating them into life as needed and being a technology literate are considered valuable for all disadvantaged people in the society such as the elderly, the disabled, women and individuals with economic or educational barriers. These people should be included in life socially, culturally and economically without any discrimination.

Given that young people grew up in a technology-intensive world, they can easily adapt to changes in technology and use computers and the Internet as an essential part of information and communication technologies, so it is extremely important to ensure that adults are technology literate. Before the disadvantages, divisions and gaps arising from the current conditions reach larger dimensions in our country, it is also of great importance to increase

the technology competences of adults, to evaluate regularly the relationship between technology and technology use, and to implement policies to ensure technology literacy depending on the results obtained. There is a distinction between people who have and use information technology and those who do not have or cannot use that technology. This division can be the biggest obstacle to the development of political and social equality and democratic society among individuals.

5. Conclusion: How to use ICT for social integration

Adult education in the 21st century faces many new challenges that result from the growing possibilities of using and integrating ICT in every aspect of both professional and personal life. The great potential lies in the development of ICT integration in the professional environment and the activation of professional life and adult education

Researchers from different countries and backgrounds give some answers on “ResearchGate” to this important question.

Technology has begun to impose itself in all aspects of life, one of the most important of these is the social aspect. [Yousif Yaqoob Yousif, Department of Educational Sciences psychological, University of Baghdad]

Earlier the teacher had his or her students within reach for oral communication in a classroom. The students did not normally interact with other than teacher and peers during class time. That is what for the teacher appeared as his or her class to teach, the learners within reach, which he used for constructing collaboration in best cases. The social qualities of interaction varied a lot - we seem to only remember the nice and ideal parts when comparing to ICT-enabled learning communication.

Today the friction of information is very low indeed, it flows through classroom walls without problems. But it creates problems for the teacher that want absolute attention. But in some cases, the teacher may not deserve this absolute attention - and students do their facebooking, listen to other teachers on the same subject on youtube or communicate with students or experts in another country - from the classroom, when a lecture is ongoing. This is a conflict - classroom does not obstruct information flows as before. On the other side, if students and teacher use these new possibilities, they can be on another level of learning communication. What says that your peers sitting physically close to you are the most important ones in your life or for learning this module? And it is clearly unlikely that the teacher is the best one to explain x to you with a student with his/her special conditions. [Anders Norberg, Department of Applied Educational Science, Umeå University]

Adults are unique in how they learn and hence the process of using ICT in adult education needs to integrate such uniqueness and provide latitude in how an adult is able to interact with others using diverse ICT platforms. [Ruth W. Mwangi, Department of Psychology, University of the Witwatersrand]

Bibliography

1. Bozer, R., (2019) 'Teknoloji Okuryazarlığı ve Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu ile Yetişkin Yeterliliklerinin Uluslararası Değerlendirilmesi Programı Verileri Kapsamında Ülkemizde Teknoloji Kullanım Durumu' Yetişkin Eğitimi Dergisi/Cilt: 2/Sayı: 2-3/Mayıs-Kasım 2019/Sayfa:166-196 -Journal of Adult Education/Volume: 2/Issue: 2-3/May-November 2019/Pages:166-196
2. Escuder-Mollon, Pilar & Esteller-Curto, Roger & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Bardus, Massimo. (2014). Impact on Senior Learners' Quality of Life through Lifelong Learning. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*. 131. 510-516. 10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.157.
3. Falcinelli, F. Laici, C. *ICT In The Classroom: A New Learning Environment*, por. source: <http://conference.pixel-online.net/FOE/acceptedabstracts.php> [access: 05.05.2016].
4. Karabacak S., Kaygın H.,(2018) 'Uluslararası Yetişkin Becerileri Araştırmasına (PIAAC) Yönelik Halk Eğitimi Merkezlerinde Görev Yapan Eğitimcilerin Görüşü' http://www.turkishstudies.net/turkishstudies?mod=tammetin&makaleadi=&makaleurl=464423998_35KarabacakSerap-vd-egt-745-762.pdf&key=21646
5. Kopeć, Wiesław, NOWE FORMY WSPARCIA I EDUKACJI ICT SENIORÓW. 01.07.2019, <https://kometa.edu.pl/artykuly/228,nowe-formy-wsparcia-i-edukacji-ict-seniorow> Accessed 13.01.2020
6. Marzano, Gilberto & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2017). CHALLENGES OF WEB-BASED PARTICIPATORY LEARNING. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. *Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference*. 2. 458. 10.17770/sie2017vol2.2395.
7. Marzano, Gilberto & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2017). Online collaborative learning: the EsCAIADE training experiment. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/323394298_Online_collaborative_learning_the_EsCAIADE_training_experiment
8. Marzano, Gilberto & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2018). LEARNING FROM THE KNOWLEDGE AND EXPERTISE OF OTHERS. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. *Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference*. 5. 137. 10.17770/sie2018vol1.3083.
9. Marzano, Gilberto & Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2019). Online Participatory Learning for Low-Qualified Adult Learners. *International Journal of Web-Based Learning and Teaching Technologies*. 14. 50-66. 10.4018/IJWLTT.2019040104.
10. Marzano, Gilberto, Lizut, Joanna, Ochoa Siguencia, Luis. (2019). DIGITAL SOCIAL INNOVATION: A PRELIMINARY PORTFOLIO OF COMPETENCIES FOR SCHOOL SOCIAL WORKERS. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. *Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference*. 2. 320. 10.17770/sie2019vol2.3864.

11. Mikołajczyk Katarzyna, „Nowe trendy w kształceniu dorosłych”, Ośrodek Rozwoju Edukacji maj 2019, https://www.researchgate.net/publication/333339666_Katarzyna_Mikołajczyk_Nowe_trendy_w_kształceniu_dorosłych Accessed 13.01.2020
12. Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Gómez-Ullate, Martin & Herman, Damian. (2015). Use of online collaborative writing tools by students of higher education. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289460617_Use_of_online_collaborative_writing_tools_by_students_of_higher_education
13. Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Herman, Damian & Marzano, Gilberto. (2015). Creating effective online collaborative learning groups at higher education institutions. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/292962563_Creating_effective_online_collaborative_learning_groups_at_higher_education_institutions
14. Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Marzano, Gilberto & Herman, Damian. (2017). INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY FOR PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF ADULT EDUCATION STAFF MANAGEMENT: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS IN THE SILESIA REGION. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. 3. 575-584. 10.17770/sie2017vol3.2385.
15. Ochoa Siguencia, Luis & Marzano, Gilberto & Ochoa-Daderska, Renata. (2016). EXPERIMENTING PARTICIPATIVE E-LEARNING IN NON-FORMAL ADULT EDUCATION: THE ESCALADE PROJECT. SOCIETY. INTEGRATION. EDUCATION. Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference. 4. 144. 10.17770/sie2016vol4.1544.
16. Ochoa Siguencia, Luis (2011). *Use of ICT in the management of educational institutions: the case of Silesian College of Economics and Administration in Bytom – Poland*. In: Proceedings of the Third International Conference on E-learning in the Workplace - ICELW 2011, New York, June 8th-10th 2011. - New York : Kaleidoscope Learning, p. 54-59
17. Ochoa-Dąderska, Renata, Czapka, Mirosław, Ochoa-Siguencia, Luis (2010). Aktywne obywatelstwo poprzez nowe technologie informacyjno-komunikacyjne w każdym wieku : projekt active-ICT : (wprowadzenie do problematyki badań własnych) // Nauczyciel i Szkoła, nr 1/2, s. 143-149
18. TEDMEM (Türkiye Eğitim Derneği) (2016). OECD Yetişkin Becerileri Araştırması: Türkiye İle İlgili Sonuçlar. Ankara: Türk Eğitim Derneği Yayınları. Erişim adresi: <https://tedmem.org/download/oecd-yetiskin-becerileri-arastirmasi-turkiye-ile-ilgili-sonuclar?wpdmdl=1688>
19. TÜİK (Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu) (2018). Hane Halkı Bilişim Teknolojileri Kullanım Araştırması 2018. Ankara: TÜİK
20. TÜİK (Türkiye İstatistik Kurumu) (2019). Hane Halkı Bilişim Teknolojileri Kullanım Araştırması 2019. Ankara: TÜİK
21. Yıldız, A., Dindar, H., Ünlü, D., Gökçe, N., Kocakurt, Ö. ve Kırıl Özüstün, A. (2018). “Yetişkin Yeterliklerinin Uluslararası Değerlendirilmesi Programı (PIACC)” Sonuçları Bağlamında Türkiye’de Temel Eğitim Sorunlarını Yeniden Düşünmek. *Ankara*

Üniversitesi Eğitim Bilimleri Fakültesi Dergisi, Yıl: 2018, Cilt: 51, Sayı: 2, 209-237.
Erişim adresi: <http://dergipark.gov.tr/download/article-file/516535>

Websites:

Title of Site. Available online: URL (accessed on Day Month Year).

1. Eurostat. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/data/database> (accessed on 23/03/2020).
2. Planes realizados en TIC y Sociedad de la Información. Available online: <https://avancedigital.gob.es/planes-TIC/agenda-digital/Paginas/planes-especificos.aspx> (accessed on 23/03/2020).
3. INE (2019), Encuesta sobre equipamiento y uso de tecnologías de información y comunicación en los hogares, INE, https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176741&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576692
4. INE (2019), Encuesta sobre el uso de TIC y comercio electrónico en las empresas, INE, https://www.ine.es/dyngs/INEbase/es/operacion.htm?c=Estadistica_C&cid=1254736176743&menu=ultiDatos&idp=1254735576692

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